

A QoE and Visual Attention Evaluation on the Influence of Spatial Audio in 360° videos

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Abstract

This paper presents a summary of an ongoing doctoral research focused on evaluating the quality of experience (QoE) and visual attention aspects of spatial audio in 360° videos. With the increasing popularity of virtual reality (VR) applications, it is crucial to understand the impact of spatial audio on user perception and engagement. The research investigates the influence of spatial audio on visual attention patterns within immersive 360° video environments in addition to subjective and objective measures of QoE. This paper provides an overview of the research objectives, experimental setup, methodology, overview of findings based on the analysis of subjective, objective and intrinsic data, and future directions.

Keywords: 360° videos, Ambisonics, Visual attention, Quality of Experience

1 Introduction

In recent years, the popularity of VR applications, particularly 360° videos, has significantly increased. These videos are experienced through Head Mounted Display (HMD) technology, offering users a more immersive and interactive viewing experience. However, streaming 360° videos to HMDs presents numerous challenges, including limited bandwidth, storage, and computational resources. Additionally, factors such as low motion-to-photon delay expectations, complex view adaptation, understanding of 360° video Quality of Experience (QoE) [Shojib et al., 2021], and the influence of visual attention [Huang and Wang, 2020] on user perception need to be understood.

Visual attention refers to the selective process through which our brains focus on specific information from our environment. It enables efficient extraction of relevant information and understanding of our surroundings. Various techniques have been developed for visual attention modeling, incorporating saliency feature vectors, object-based attention, and salient maps. Understanding visual attention is crucial for optimizing video content and delivery, ultimately enhancing the user experience.

While visual attention has received considerable research attention, the impact of audio, particularly spatial audio, on visual attention in immersive media has been relatively overlooked [Kim et al., 2020]. Current research predominantly focuses on analyzing attention in conventional non-spatial sound videos, neglecting the immersive multimedia context. Spatial audio, which adds depth and directionality to sound, has gained attention for its ability to create a more realistic VR experience. Investigating the role of spatial audio in visual attention is essential for enhancing the overall quality of VR experiences [Xylakis et al., 2020].

Ambisonics, a technique for capturing and reproducing 360° audio, has gained popularity due to its ability to provide an immersive audio experience in VR [Innes and Shellard, 2005]. This technique involves recording sound from all directions and encoding it into a multi-channel format, enhancing the sense of presence and realism. Higher-order Ambisonics formats offer greater spatial resolution and immersion, enabling precise localization of sound sources [Politis et al., 2018].

With the increasing adoption of VR and 360° videos, understanding the Quality of Experience (QoE) has become paramount. QoE encompasses the overall subjective user experience while interacting with multimedia applications and is influenced by factors such as content quality [Raake, 2014], network conditions [Xue et al., 2011], device performance [Singh and Kapoor, 2018], and user expectations [Li et al., 2016]. In the context of VR

and 360° videos, QoE plays a crucial role in determining the level of immersion and presence experienced by users [Wang and Li, 2021]. Investigating QoE provides valuable insights into user preferences [Shahriar and Shiratori, 2015], behavior [Ahmed et al., 2019], and perception [Wang et al., 2016], allowing the design of more effective and engaging applications.

This doctoral study explores the impact of different sound conditions, including no sound, first-order ambisonics(FOA) sound, high-order ambisonics(HOA) sound, and stereo sound, on visual attention and QoE of participants watching 360° videos wearing a VR headset. The study involves analyzing objective (head pose, eye gaze fixations), intrinsic (pupil diameter, heart rate) and subjective data (user questionnaire) to provide insights into the impact of spatial audio on visual attention and QoE in 360° videos.

The remainder of this paper is organized as follows: Section 2 provides an overview of state-of-the-art, Section 3 describes the experimental setup, Section 4 outlines the research methodology, and Section 5 presents details about the dataset. Section 6 presents the statistical analysis of the subjective questionnaire, and finally, Section 7 concludes the paper and discusses future work.

2 State of the Art

Numerous studies have examined visual attention in 360° videos, shedding light on the subject over the past decade. [Jean et al., 2017] conducted research on viewer attention in 360° videos and created a dataset containing sensor data and content information. The dataset consisted of ten YouTube videos categorized into three groups: Computer Generated (fast-paced), Natural Image (fast-paced), and Natural Image (slow-paced). Viewer orientations were captured using OpenTrack, an open-source head tracking tool integrated with HMD sensors.

[David et al., 2018] presented a publicly available dataset of head and eye movements recorded during a free-view trial where participants wore VR headsets equipped with eye trackers. The dataset encompassed 360° videos played without audio and included saliency maps and scan paths in addition to the videos. The impact of sound on visual attention in 360° videos was explored by [Chunjia et al., 2014]. They conducted eye-tracking tests with 60 videos under various conditions: videos with audio-video (AV) and videos without audio (V). Their findings suggested that the effect of sound depended on the consistency between visual and audio signals. Interestingly, they discovered that audio had minimal or no influence on visual attention when the sound sources precisely matched the salient objects in the video. However, when the sound sources differed from the salient objects, they tended to attract participants' attention.

[Marighetto et al., 2017] investigated the influence of audio on visual attention in non-360° videos. Their eye-tracking dataset comprised eye positions recorded during four eye-tracking studies. Participants watched videos under different audio conditions (with or without sound) and visual groups (moving objects, landscapes, and faces). The study revealed that audio-visual content consistently resulted in less dispersion of eye gaze compared to visual-only content. The presence or absence of sound influenced the spatial distribution of eye gaze, particularly in the face category. [Wu et al., 2017] introduced a head tracking dataset containing user behaviour patterns in VR applications. The dataset included data from 48 users watching 18 spherical videos across five categories. Users' head movements, directions of focus, and remembered content after each session were recorded. However, the videos were accompanied by non-spatial sound.

Additionally, [Almquist and Almquist, 2018] investigated the viewing behaviours of subjects experiencing various 360° videos from different categories using HMDs. Data related to head orientation and rotation speed was collected through the HMD sensors as the subjects watched the videos. The study found that the distribution of viewing angles heavily depended on the content of the video, with viewers spending considerable time looking at the front in the Static Focus and Rides categories. The Exploration and Moving Focus categories exhibited a nearly linear distribution, with yaw rotation being the most common compared to pitch and roll rotations.

These studies have contributed valuable insights into visual attention and the role of audio in immersive media. However, the novelty of this research lies in its approach to evaluating visual attention and QoE in 360° videos. Specifically, the research utilizes head pose and eye gaze data to assess visual attention. This approach goes beyond analysing only head movements or eye-tracking data to gain insights into the specific elements of the video

that viewers are focusing on. By incorporating eye gaze data alongside head pose data, a deeper understanding of viewer engagement with the content in 360° videos can be achieved. Moreover, the research evaluates QoE through pupil dilation measurements and subjective questionnaires. Pupil dilation is a physiological response that has been linked to cognitive and emotional processing. By analysing pupil dilation, researchers can gain insights into viewers' cognitive and emotional responses to the 360° videos. This comprehensive approach provides a more holistic understanding of the user experience beyond relying solely on traditional subjective questionnaires. Additionally, the research explores the influence of different audio types on visual attention and QoE in 360° videos. This aspect is of significant importance as audio can have a profound impact on the viewer's overall experience of the video.

3 Experimental set up and presentation systems

3.1 Experimental Setup

This section provides an overview of the experimental setup, including details on the laboratory design, the presentation system used for immersive media, and the techniques employed to capture user head pose, gaze, and physiological data.

3.1.1 Laboratory Design

The laboratory design followed the recommendations outlined in [ISO 8589, 2007], which provides guidelines for designing test rooms for sensory analysis. Fig. 1 illustrates a test subject participating in the experiment within our laboratory. Table 1 outlines the hardware and software components utilized for the experiment.

3.1.2 Presentation System

3.1.2.1 Selection of 360-degree videos

For the experiment, a set of ten 360° videos with FOA and HOA sound were chosen from a pool of recordings available at [Farina, 2020]. The selection criteria considered factors such as video length, content, resolution, and Ambisonics sound order. The videos were divided into two categories: indoor and outdoor, with five videos in each category. Within these categories, the videos were further subcategorized as Opera, Instrument, Riding, and Exploration. To ensure impartial presentation to participants, the videos were randomly stitched together to form two 300-second (60-sec * 5) segments—one for the indoor category and one for the outdoor category—using the ffmpeg [Ffmpeg, 2021] tool. The selected videos were processed to have a duration of 60 seconds each, stitched together, and the Ambisonics sound was converted to stereo for non-spatial audio experience or removed entirely. The videos did not include any narrative or subtitles.

The five videos in the Indoor category depicted an Opera performance with actors on an elevated platform and an orchestra performing below the platform. The camera remained stationary, positioned between the platform and the orchestra. Each video began with the participant facing the stage where the actors were performing. The other five videos belonged to the Outdoor category and were exploratory in nature, lacking a specific focal point for immediate visual interest. These videos contained sound-emitting objects, some of which were stationary, such as a clock tower or a person playing a musical instrument while seated, while others were in motion, such as people talking while walking or ducks quacking while wading in water. Fig.2 shows some of the representative frames for videos in the Indoor and Outdoor categories.

3.1.2.2 Video presentation

The GoPro VR player [GoPro, 2020], a free 360° video player, was employed to present the videos on the HTC Vive headset with an integrated Tobii Pro eye tracker [Pro, 2018]. The VR player transmitted 360° video playback

information, including camera orientation, video URL, playback status, and playback position, to a port on the system running the experiment. This allowed viewers to watch the 360° videos from any orientation, with their movements recorded as yaw, pitch, and roll angles (refer to Fig. 3a, b, and c).

3.1.2.3 Audio presentation

Although the HTC Vive headset came with an audio strap providing integrated earphones, the Beyerdynamic DT 990 Pro headphones [Beyerdynamic, 2020] were utilized to present the various forms of audio. These headphones feature larger open-back ear cups, which facilitate more natural and clear hearing, as recommended by the manufacturer.

3.1.3 Head Pose, Gaze, Pupil Diameter, and Heart-rate Data Acquisition

Python scripts were developed to capture pose, gaze, and pupil diameter data for each frame of the 360° video sequence. The pose data included the yaw, pitch, and roll angles measured in radians. Gaze data recorded the X and Y coordinates of the participant's point of focus on the screen, while pupil diameter data measured the size of the participant's pupils. The collected data was saved in CSV files for each participant, which were subsequently used for data analysis purposes. The integration of the Tobii Pro eye tracker with the HTC Vive headset allowed for simultaneous recording of pose and gaze data, enabling the analysis of the correlation between head movement and visual attention.

To collect heart rate data, we utilized the E4 wristband [Empatica, 2023], a medical-grade wearable device that offers real-time data acquisition and software for in-depth analysis and visualization. Following the official installation guide, we set up the hardware, and the E4 Connect application was used to capture physiological

Figure 1: Participant experiencing the VR environment in our lab

Figure 3a, b, c: Yaw, Pitch and Roll angles adapted from [28]

Figure 2: Representative frames for Indoor and Outdoor scenes (Top – Opera Stage, Orchestra; Bottom – Town square with clock tower, Man riding a motorbike with two dogs following)

Component	Vendor/Specifications	Used For
PC	Intel Core™ i5 – 4590 CPU @ 3.30GHz, 10.0 GB RAM, 16GB nVidia GTX 970 Graphics Card, Windows 10	Running the hardware and software for the immersive environment
HMD	HTC Vive with Tobii Pro VR Integration	Watching 360° videos
Headphones	Beyerdynamic DT 990 Pro	Listening to non-spatial/spatial audio
360° Player	GoPro VR Player	Playing 360° videos to the HMD, obtaining head orientation as yaw, pitch and roll
360° videos		Audio-visual presentation to participants
Wristband	E4	Collecting physiological data

Table 1: Experiment setup components

data during the experiment.

Overall, the experimental setup included a controlled laboratory environment designed according to ISO standards. The presentation system employed the GoPro VR player for video playback on the HTC Vive headset, with audio presented through Beyerdynamic headphones. Head pose, gaze, and pupil diameter data were captured using Python scripts and the Tobii Pro eye tracker integrated with the headset. Additionally, heart rate data was recorded using the E4 wristband. These data acquisition techniques allowed for comprehensive analysis of user responses and behaviours during the viewing of 360° videos.

4 Methodology

The research methodology employed in this study follows an experimental evaluation approach, drawing inspiration from various sources such as [Keighrey et al., 2017], [Hynes et al., 2019], [Egan et al., 2016], and ITU-T recommendation P.913 [ITU, 2016].

4.1 Participants

A convenience sampling approach was used to recruit a total of 73 participants, consisting of 45 men and 28 women, with an average age of 29 years. Among the participants, 26 had prior experience with VR, while 26 had no prior experience. VR experience was not recorded for the remaining 19 participants, who were the initial participants when the study began.

4.2 Assessment Protocol

The assessment protocol consisted of five main phases: the information phase (10 minutes), screening phase (10 minutes), training phase (5 minutes), testing phase (10 minutes), and a subjective questionnaire (5-10 minutes).

During the information phase, participants were provided with detailed information about the experiment and had the opportunity to ask questions before signing a consent form. The screening phase involved evaluating participants' visual and auditory acuity, as well as screening for colour perception using tests such as Snellen [Provisu, 2021] and Ishihara [Colblindor, 2021], and an auditory test [Pigeon, 2020]. In the training phase, participants watched a 60-second 360° video to familiarize themselves with the VR environment and underwent a calibration process. The testing phase consisted of participants watching two 300-second, 360° video segments, one recorded indoors and the other outdoors in one of the four sound conditions (no sound, stereo, FOA, or HOA sound). Finally, each participant answered a subjective questionnaire that assessed their perception of presence, immersion, and spatiality of sound after watching the stimuli. The entire assessment took approximately 40-50 minutes on average.

4.3 Questionnaire and Rating Scale

A questionnaire comprising twenty questions [Hirway, 2023] was developed to evaluate participants' perception of presence, immersion, and spatiality of sound. Inputs from [Rigby et al., 2019] and [UC Lab, 2004] were considered during the questionnaire development process. The questionnaire utilized the absolute category rating (ACR) system described in [ITU, 2016]. Participants rated each question using a five-point Likert scale, indicating their level of agreement or disagreement with each statement.

5 Dataset description

The dataset used in this study consists of ten videos, five in the indoor category and five in the outdoor category. Each video has a duration of 60 seconds, resulting in a total of 600 seconds of video playback for each participant. The videos are numbered and categorized accordingly. Participants watched the videos in a randomized order within

each category, with the indoor sequence played first, followed by the outdoor sequence. Each participant experienced only one sound condition across all the videos, which was randomly selected from options such as no sound, stereo, FOA, or HOA sound.

The dataset is organized into eight folders: foin, fout, hoin, hout, nsin, nsout, stin, and stout. Each folder corresponds to a sound condition in both indoor and outdoor environments. Within each folder, there are three subfolders: gaze data (`_gazedata`), heart rate data (`_HR`), and pose data (`_posedata`). The gaze data includes information about gaze and pupil diameter for both the left and right eyes. The pose data contains yaw and pitch information, representing head movement. The heart rate data captures participants' heart rate during the experiment. The data is stored in CSV files, with file names indicating the type of data, timestamp, and sequence of videos watched by the participant.

The gaze data consists of 146 files, with approximately 36,000 samples in each file, capturing the participants' gaze information throughout the 43,800 seconds of video playback. The heart rate data comprises 73 files, providing information on heart rate in different conditions. The pose data includes 146 files, each containing around 36,000 samples, representing participants' head pose during the video sequences.

We have included a subset of files from the complete dataset to provide readers with representative examples showcasing the data's characteristics and structure. [Hirway, 2023].

6 Statistical Analysis of Subjective Questionnaire

An ANOVA was conducted with a 95% confidence level to compare the mean responses between the sound condition groups. The results indicate that sound conditions influenced participants' ability to retain attention, conscious awareness of the real world, perception of experiencing the content, enjoyment of the experience, engagement of senses, and naturalness of interaction. HOA sound consistently received the highest mean responses for these measures, followed by FOA sound and stereo.

The findings from the analysis of the subjective questionnaire [Hirway, 2023] suggest that the presence and nature of sound significantly impact users' immersive experience and quality of interaction while watching the 360° videos. Participants reported higher levels of attention retention, enjoyment, engagement of senses, and perceived naturalness of interaction when exposed to HOA sound compared to other sound conditions. The use of spatially accurate sound, such as HOA, appeared to enhance the overall immersion and presence within the virtual environment. Furthermore, the absence of sound seemed to increase participants' conscious awareness of the real world, indicating that sound can serve as a means of distraction from external surroundings. The perception of experiencing the content, rather than just watching it, was also enhanced by the presence of sound, with participants reporting a greater sense of immersion and involvement in the virtual environment.

These findings have implications for content creators and developers of immersive media. They highlight the importance of carefully considering sound design and its spatial characteristics when aiming to create captivating and engaging experiences for users. The use of HOA sound, in particular, can offer a more realistic and immersive auditory environment, providing users with a heightened sense of presence and a natural interaction with the content. Overall, the statistical analysis of the subjective questionnaire underscores the significance of sound conditions in shaping users' perception, immersion, and quality of experience in virtual environments.

7 Conclusions and Future Work

In conclusion, the research conducted thus far has made significant contributions to understanding visual attention in the context of 360° videos. By analysing a comprehensive dataset that captures viewers' responses to different sound conditions, valuable insights have been gained regarding their visual attention, physiological reactions, and subjective perceptions. The findings shed light on the impact of sound on immersive experiences and offer important considerations for optimizing content delivery in VR and 360° videos.

One of the key findings of this research is the influence of HOA sound on viewers' physiological arousal.

The data revealed that when participants watched videos with HOA sound, their heart rate increased, indicating heightened physiological arousal compared to other sound conditions. This suggests that the complexity and richness of spatial audio can induce a stronger physiological response and potentially enhance the overall engagement and immersion of viewers. Moreover, the analysis of gaze fixations demonstrated that videos with spatial audio resulted in more evenly distributed gaze patterns. Participants exhibited a more comprehensive exploration of the visual content when immersed in environments with HOA sound. This suggests that spatial audio has the potential to guide and shape viewers' visual attention, creating a more captivating and interactive viewing experience.

Subjective ratings provided by the participants further supported the benefits of HOA sound. The HOA sound condition consistently received the highest ratings for realism and clarity, indicating its superiority over stereo and FOA sound. This finding emphasizes the importance of incorporating spatial audio techniques, specifically HOA, to enhance the perceived quality and authenticity of virtual environments.

Looking ahead, future work will focus on conducting joint correlation analysis to delve deeper into the relationships between participants' head pose, pupil diameter, eye gaze, and heart rate data. By examining these variables in conjunction, researchers can uncover intricate patterns and uncover hidden connections that may not be apparent when analysing each factor individually. This integrated approach will provide a more comprehensive understanding of viewers' behaviour and physiological responses during immersive experiences, ultimately contributing to the development of more effective and engaging VR and 360° video content.

Additionally, the dataset collected for this research will continue to serve as a valuable resource for researchers in the field. It can be utilized for further investigations and advancements in VR and 360° video technologies, enabling other scholars to explore different aspects of visual attention and immersive experiences. By sharing this dataset, the research community can collaboratively work towards enhancing the understanding of human perception in virtual environments and contribute to the development of more immersive and captivating virtual experiences.

Acknowledgements

This research is supported by Science Foundation Ireland and the ADAPT Centre under Grant Number 12/RC/2106.

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